

Yield potential

Heritability of primary root length

N. G. Hajra, S. G. Hajra, RRII, North Eastern Research Complex, P.O. Kunjaban, Tripura 799006; and P. Bairagi, Botany Department, Burdwan University, Burdwan 713104, India

In rice, as in most cereals, root systems show high variability because the genes controlling them come under environmental influences. We crossed 11 varieties having good and poor root systems and obtained 7 cross-combinations. Seedlings were grown in test tubes with White's medium. Primary root length was recorded at 28 d and different parameters estimated to indicate the nature and degree of improvement by hybridization in F₂ generation. CH1040/ NC918 and CH47/CH63 were relatively stable, with low response to environment. The five other crosses were highly responsive to environmental fluctuations, requiring

repeated selection in advanced generations of the best 5% of the population.

The F₂ lines provide a prediction of the genetic advance, or improvement

expected. The primary root length showed a moderately high heritability in each cross (82.4 to 52.3%), although the estimated numbers of effective factors were low (see table). □

Genetic parameters of primary root length in 7 rice crosses.

Parameter ^a	Larkoch/ NC918	CH10/ NC918	CH1040/ NC918	CH47/ CH63	CH988/ CHI7	Badkalamkati 65/CH4	Boak/ NC918
<i>Mean (cm)</i>							
\bar{P}_1	8.73	10.80	9.13	11.13	10.93	18.03	15.07
\bar{P}_2	18.80	18.80	18.80	20.73	17.27	18.43	18.80
$(\bar{P}_1 + \bar{P}_2) / 2$	13.77	14.80	13.97	15.93	14.10	18.33	16.53
\bar{F}_1	14.80	13.70	13.60	19.30	19.00	18.68	16.10
\bar{F}_2	15.80	14.00	12.30	16.20	20.01	22.03	19.47
<i>Variance</i>							
VP ₁	3.86	4.29	3.38	3.64	5.26	5.59	4.46
VP ₂	5.23	5.23	5.23	6.00	5.86	5.54	5.23
VE	4.54	4.76	4.30	4.82	5.56	5.01	4.34
VF ₂	25.83	12.27	9.04	11.43	18.73	14.08	12.38
VG	21.28	7.51	4.74	6.60	13.17	9.07	7.54
GA	8.63	4.42	3.25	4.02	6.27	4.98	4.41
<i>Heritability</i>							
h ² (%)	82.4	6.20	52.39	57.78	10.30	64.41	60.88
<i>Estimated effective factors</i>							
K	0.59 ≈ 1	1.07 ≈ 1	2.46 ≈ 2	1.74 ≈ 2	0.38 ≈ 0	0	0.23 = 0

^aVG = genetic variance, GA = genetic advance, VP₁ and VP₂ = variation of first and second parents, VE = environmental-variance, VF₂ = variation of F₂ population, \bar{P}_1 and \bar{P}_2 = av root length of parent one and two, \bar{F}_1 and \bar{F}_2 = av primary root length of F₁ and F₂ hybrids.

Rice panicle characteristics

S. Mallik A. M. Aguilar, and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, IIRI

We studied panicle characteristics of 10 IR varieties, 16 *O. glaberrima* accessions, and 16 lines from a cross involving upland rice parents. High

density (HD) grains, having specific gravity >1.20, are found mostly on primary branches of rice panicles. Increasing the percentage of HD grains by decreasing the number of secondary branches can increase rice yield potential. The number of HD grains may also improve with better delivery system of the assimilates, such as more

vascular bundles, and bigger culms or thicker culms.

The *glaberrimas* had comparatively more primary branches and more spikelets on primary branches than did IR and upland entries (Table 1). They also had fewer secondary branches—the location of most low density grains—and fewer spikelets on them. □

Table 1. Range and mean of 10 panicle characters in 3 types of rice varieties. IIRI, 1988.

Character	Range			Mean		
	IR varieties	O. glaberrima	Upland	IR varieties	O. glaberrima	Upland
1. Primary branches (no.) (Pbr)	7 - 16.3	8 - 16.3	7.7- 14.7	10.3 ± 0.7	13.1 ± 0.7	12.1 ± 0.5
2. Spikelets on Pbr (no.) (SPbr)	37 -124	51 -139	38.3- 91.3	60.2 ± 7.5	99.3 ± 7.0	70.6 ± 3.7
3. Secondary branches (no.) (Sbr)	18.8- 34.8	2.2- 27.7	5.7- 39	26.7 ± 2.0	12.8 ± 1.9	27 ± 2.8
4. Spikelets on Sbr (no.) (SSbr)	60.3-117	4.7- 59.7	12.3-130.7	87.3 ± 6.4	33.2 ± 5.6	85 ± 9.6
5. Total spikelets (no.) (TSP)	100 -241	91 -199	51 -208	147.5 ± 12.2	132.4 ± 7.2	155.5 ± 12.7
6. Inner vascular bundle (no.) (IVB)	14 - 25.5	13.7- 18.7	9 - 22.7	19.9 ± 1.1	15.8 ± 0.4	16.0 ± 0.9
7. Outer vascular bundle (no.) (OVB)	16.8- 30.5	17.3- 36	13.7- 34.5	21 ± 1.2	34.1 ± 9.3	24.8 ± 1.7
8. Culm diameter (mm) (CD)	2.1- 3.2	1.6- 2.6	1.3- 3	2.3 ± 0.1	2 ± 0.1	2.4 ± 0.1
9. Air space (mm) (Asp)	1.5- 2.4	0.8- 1.8	0.6- 2.1	1.7 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.1	1.5 ± 0.1
10. Culm thickness ^a (mm) (Cth)	0.3- 0.4	0.3- 0.5	0.3- 0.6	0.3 ± 0.01	0.4 ± 0.01	0.4 ± 0.02

^aCth = (CD - ASP)/2.